

A Short Note on the Infinity Product Tan (z) Function

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Abstract: We derive the infinite product of the tangent function, $\text{Tan}(z)$, expressed in terms of trigonometric expressions such as Euler's Sinc function and Viète's formula, along with their generalizations. All the results presented in this work are novel.

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1. Introduction

Infinite product (1) was previously published by Viète in 1593, based on geometric considerations. A detailed compendium, including analysis and evaluations of infinite products of elementary functions in terms of trigonometric functions, can be found in the classical literature

$$\prod_{k=0}^{\infty} \cos(\pi 2^{-k-2}) = \frac{2}{\pi} \quad (1)$$

Viète's formula is the following infinite product of nested radicals

$$\frac{1}{8} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{2}+2)(\sqrt{\sqrt{2}+2+2})(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{2}+2+2+2}})} = \frac{2}{\pi} \quad (2)$$

Viète's formula may be obtained as a special case of a formula for the sinc function that has often been attributed to Leonhard Euler[1], more than a century later:

$$\prod_{k=0}^{\infty} \cos(2^{-k-1}z) = \frac{\sin(z)}{z} \quad (3)$$

expressing each term of the product on the left as a function of earlier terms using the half-angle formula:

$$\cos\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\cos(z)+1)} \quad (4)$$

gives Viète's formula

This formula has been generalization obtained through use of both Chebyshev polynomial and Fourier transformation (see Nishimura [3] and Kent E. Morrison [2]) for integer $q \geq 2$. As

$$\prod_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{\sum_{n=1}^q \cos\left(\frac{(2n-1)z}{(2q)^{j+1}}\right)}{q} = \frac{\sin(z)}{z} \quad (5)$$

This can be written in more compact way

$$\prod_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(zq^{-k}) \csc(zq^{-k-1})}{q} = \text{sinc}(z) \quad (6)$$

2. The Tan Function

We present two new generalizations of the infinite product of the tangent function in the style of Leonhard Euler's $\text{sinc}(z)$ type. $q \geq 2$.

$$\prod_{k=0}^{\infty} 2^{-((q-1)q^k)} q^{-q^k(k(q-1)+q)} z^{(q-1)q^k} \cot^{q^{k+1}}\left(\frac{1}{2}zq^{-k-1}\right) \cot^{-q^k}\left(\frac{zq^{-k}}{2}\right) = \frac{2 \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)}{z} \quad (7)$$

And the equivalent convergent product

$$\prod_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\tan\left(\frac{zq^{-k}}{2}\right) \cot\left(\frac{1}{2}zq^{-k-1}\right)}{q} = \frac{2 \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)}{z} \quad (8)$$

3. Generalization.

It is possible to generalize (7) and (8) so that n and m are integers $\{n, m\} \geq 0$ as following:

$$\begin{aligned} & \prod_{k=m}^{n-1} 2^{-((q-1)q^k)} q^{-q^k(k(q-1)+q)} z^{(q-1)q^k} \sin^{-q^{k+1}}\left(\frac{1}{2}zq^{-k-1}\right) \sin^{q^k}\left(\frac{zq^{-k}}{2}\right) \cos^{q^{k+1}}\left(\frac{1}{2}zq^{-k-1}\right) \cos^{-q^k}\left(\frac{zq^{-k}}{2}\right) \\ & = 2^{q^m - q^n} q^{mq^m - nq^n} z^{q^n - q^m} \sin^{q^m}\left(\frac{zq^{-m}}{2}\right) \cos^{-q^m}\left(\frac{zq^{-m}}{2}\right) \sin^{-q^n}\left(\frac{zq^{-n}}{2}\right) \cos^{q^n}\left(\frac{zq^{-n}}{2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} & \prod_{k=m}^{n-1} \frac{\tan\left(\frac{zq^{-k}}{2}\right) \cot\left(\frac{1}{2}zq^{-k-1}\right)}{q} \\ & = q^{m-n} \tan\left(\frac{zq^{-m}}{2}\right) \cot\left(\frac{zq^{-n}}{2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

For brevity, we employ mathematical induction to prove the case of Formula (10) when $q = 2$ and $m = 0$

Proof: starting with

$$\prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-k-1}z) \cot(2^{-k-2}z) = 2^{-n} \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \cot(2^{-n-1}z) \quad (11)$$

Step 1: Base Case $n = 1$ We need to show that the formula holds for $n = 1$: the left-hand side LHS becomes:

$$\frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-1-1}z) \cot(2^{-1-2}z) = \frac{1}{2} \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \cot\left(\frac{z}{4}\right) \quad (12)$$

The right-hand side RHS becomes:

$$2^{-1} \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \cot(2^{-1-1}z) = \frac{1}{2} \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \cot\left(\frac{z}{4}\right) \quad (13)$$

The LHS and RHS are equal for the base case.

Step 2: Inductive Hypothesis Assume that the formula is true for some arbitrary positive integer n :

$$\prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-k-1}z) \cot(2^{-k-2}z) = 2^{-n} \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \cot(2^{-n-1}z) \quad (14)$$

Step 3: Inductive Step We need to prove that the formula holds for $n + 1$: Consider the LHS for $n + 1$:

$$\prod_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-k-1}z) \cot(2^{-k-2}z) \quad (15)$$

Multiply both sides by $\left(\frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-n-1}z) \cot(2^{-n-2}z)\right)$:

$$\left(\prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-k-1}z) \cot(2^{-k-2}z)\right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-n-1}z) \cot(2^{-n-2}z) \quad (16)$$

Using the inductive hypothesis, the RHS simplifies to:

$$2^{-n} \tan\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \cot(2^{-n-1}z) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \tan(2^{-n-1}z) \cot(2^{-n-2}z) \quad (17)$$

Simplify the RHS:

$$2^{-n-1} \tan\left(\frac{Z}{2}\right) \cot(2^{-n-1}z) \quad (18)$$

The RHS matches the LHS for $(n + 1)$.

Therefore, by mathematical induction, the given formula holds for all positive integers (n)

Example 1. Infinitely nested radicals

Using several values for n Integers $\frac{2n \tan(\frac{\pi}{2n})}{\pi}$ in formula (10) get the following tables:

Product ∞	Result
$\frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}} \dots$	$\frac{4}{\pi}$
$\frac{(2-\sqrt{3})(2+\sqrt{3})\left(\frac{1}{4}\sqrt{3(2-\sqrt{2})(1+\sqrt{2})}+\frac{1}{4}(-1+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}\right)}{4\sqrt{3}\left(\frac{1}{4}\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}(1+\sqrt{2})}-\frac{1}{4}(-1+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{3(2+\sqrt{2})}\right)} \dots$	$\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{\pi}$
$\frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{(2-\sqrt{2})(2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}})}{(2+\sqrt{2})(2-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}})}} \dots$	$\frac{8\sqrt{\frac{2-\sqrt{2}}{2+\sqrt{2}}}}{\pi}$
$\frac{\sqrt{1-\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}}\left(\frac{1}{8}(-1+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}(-1+\sqrt{5})+\frac{1}{4}(1+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(2-\sqrt{2})(5+\sqrt{5})}\right)}{4\left(-\frac{1}{8}\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}(1+\sqrt{2})}(-1+\sqrt{5})+\frac{1}{4}(-1+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(2+\sqrt{2})(5+\sqrt{5})}\right)} \dots$	$\frac{10\sqrt{1-\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}}}{\pi}$
	$\frac{12(2-\sqrt{3})}{\pi}$
$\frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{(2-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}})(2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}})}{(2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}})(2-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}})} \dots$	$\frac{16\sqrt{\frac{2-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2+\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}}}{\pi}$

Table 1.

References

[1] Euler, Leonhard (1738). "De variis modis circuli quadraturam numeris proxime exprimendi"

[2] Kent E. Morrison (1995) Cosine Products, Fourier Transforms, and Random Sums, The American Mathematical Monthly, 102:8, 716-724, DOI: 10.1080/00029890.1995.12004647.

[3] R. Nishimura. A generalization of Viète's infinite product and new mean iterations. The Australian Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications, 13(1), 2016.